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Remuneration and Employee Performance of Selected Hotels in the Hospitality Industry in Delta State

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of remuneration on employee performance in the Nigerian hospitality industry. The study was based on agency theory, stakeholder theory, social exchange theory, and incentive contract theory. The study adopts descriptive survey designs. The study population was 407, and the sample of the study was 202 respondents, which were selected using a random sampling technique. The survey method of data collection was used. The closed-ended questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection. Data were analyzed using multiple regression analysis in SPSS Version 21. The findings of the study revealed that there are positive and significant effects of remuneration on the performance of employees in the hospitality industry, whereby, The results from the analysis show that salary has positive and significant effects on employee performance ($0.00332 < 0.05$); incentive has positive and significant effects on employee performance ($0.0024 < 0.05$); compensation benefits has positive and significant effects on employee performance ($0.00335 < 0.05$); and employee stock ownership plan has positive and significant effects on employee performance ($0.0017 < 0.05$). The study concludes that remuneration has positive and significant effects on employee performance in the hospitality industry in Nigeria. The study recommends that firms review the wage structure in order to motivate employees to retain their jobs and increase performance. The study further recommends that organizations should seek to maintain good relationships with their employees by offering good incentives in the form of financial and non-financial compensation.

Keywords: Delta State, Employee Performance, Hospitality Industry, Hotels, Remuneration.

INTRODUCTION

Human resource is the most important asset of any organisation and should be given the highest priority, as it provides the basis for sustainable competitive advantage. Organisations need to develop strategies to acquire and retain competent workforce in order to achieve efficient and effective results (Zaman, 2011). Remuneration is traditionally seen as the total income of an individual, and organizations need highly performing individuals to meet goals, deliver products and services, and achieve high performance (Buchan, Thompson & O'May, 2010). Performance is rewarded by financial and other benefits, and high performers get promoted more easily and have better career opportunities (VanScotter, Motowidlo & Cross, 2019).

Employees are the organization's key resource and their willingness to stay depends on their remuneration packages and reward system (Armstrong, 2016). Compensation management is a complex task that requires integrating employees' processes and information with business process and strategies to achieve optimal organizational goals and objectives (Fadugba, 2021; Falola, Ibidunni & Olokundun, 2020; Adeniyi, 2013). Remuneration is an essential tool to integrate individual efforts with strategic business objectives and is linked to employee performance. Companies are attempting to identify innovative strategies to improve employee performance in an ever-competitive, dynamic and changing business environment (Adeniyi, 2017; Schell & Solomon, 2017; Barret, 2016; Denis & Michel, 2016 and Inés & Pedro, 2015; Okwuise, Ugherughe & Afunwa, 2017; Okwuise, Oghoghomeh & Kifordu, 2020; Okwuise, Kifordu & Oghoghomeh, 2020; Okwuise & Ugherughe, 2023). Companies tend to provide financial remuneration and employee benefits to retain employees and improve their quality of life, which has created a competitive environment (Long, 2017 and Ali & Raza, 2015).

The Nigerian Business Report (2021) states that: "the hotel and hospitality sector is the world's largest industry and generator of jobs". It is among the fastest expanding industries in the world and is important top foreign earners for Nigeria. Hotels and recreation centers recorded a growth of 5.0 per cent in 2017 compared to 4.2 per cent in 2015, and tourism earnings increased compared to the previous years. Wood (2015) suggests that hospitality employees have no career structure and that their jobs are perceived as dead ends, making the firms less likely to attract long stay recruits. This is why many university graduates and related certificate holders sojourn at the hospitality industry as they await to determine their career path.

Employees are the most important assets in any organisation, and in the hotel industry, remuneration is of paramount importance. The motivation of the employees is a major issue as it directly corresponds to employee turnover and overall quality of service of the concerned hotels (SHIK, 2017; Chen, 2013). Zhang (2016) opined that the performance of the employees plays an important role in determining the profitability of the hotels, as employees are one of the most vital assets of the hotels. Additionally, the guests have direct interaction with the employees and the employees are responsible for satisfying the guests. Nigeria has a high rate of employees leaving their employers due to low pay, leading to a need for a study to determine if remuneration affects employee performance in the hospitality industry (Ali and Raza, 2015). Incentives can lead to improved motivation, effort, and performance, but if poorly designed or communicated, they can lead to degradation in performance. The lack of adequate remuneration policies can lead to increases in service costs, making performance-related pay schemes costlier than expected.

The hospitality sector in Nigeria has experienced problems with performance-related remuneration policies, leading to job dissatisfaction and high employee turnover. Remuneration can be successful in improving employee performance and organizational change, but its true impact remains under-researched. This study examined effects of remuneration on employee performance of selected hotels in Delta State.

The following questions are raised to guide the study: What are the effects of salary on employee performance at selected hotels in Delta State? What are the effects of incentives on the employee performance of selected hotels in Delta State? What are the effects of compensation benefits on employee performance at selected hotels in Delta State? And what are the effects of the employee stock ownership plan on the employee performance of selected hotels in Delta State?

Having seen the research questions upon which the research hypotheses of this study are built, the rest of the study is divided into four sections: the review of related literature; the conceptual framework, theoretical framework, and empirical review; the methods and materials; the results and discussion; and the conclusion and recommendations.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This section presents the conceptual review, theoretical review, empirical review and summary of literature reviewed.

Concept of Remuneration

Remuneration is the aggregate income of an individual, and can include fundamental pay, wages, wellbeing plans, pension plans, transport remittances, over time recompenses and responsibility stipends (Baker & Demerouti, 2017). Remuneration is a technique for promoting morale, increasing inspiration and encouraging team cohesion (Xanthopoulou, 2019 and Calvin, 2017). It can be as simple as a raise or advancement, but can also be powerful in long-term inspiration and profitability. It is trusted that compensation strategy represents one of the best speculations an organization makes, as money can directly impact conduct. The impact of compensation system is an essential ingredient in each association and worker execution is a basic issue for some organizations (Bauer, 2016; Coyle & Conway, 2014; Christensen, 2011 and Baker et al, 2007).

The need to attract, persuade, develop and hold employees is essential for association success, and remuneration is one of the most important determinants of employee attitudes, inspiration and behaviours. Pay is regulated to ensure a decent execution level in the workplace, and when higher outcomes result in high pay increases, execution is strengthened and more prone to be rehashed later (Knippenberg, 2017; Baker & Demerouti, 2017; Wayne, 2012; Peterson, 2011; Masterson, 2010).

Remuneration is an effective investment for organizations, as it is seen as a motivator by employees as well as managers, leading to higher levels of productivity and motivation (Christensen et al, 2011 and Xanthopoulou, 2019). When employees are inspired by striking remunerations, their performance increases and they are more likely to move towards organizational objectives without resistance (Detert, 2017 and Xanthopoulou, 2019). Employees' satisfaction depends on their expectations and how they are fulfilled. Low payments lead to lower motivation and lower performance (Peterson, 2011; Crossman & Zaki, 2013 and Shields, 2015).

Organisations must offer non-monetary benefits such as prestige, promotion, and acknowledgment to motivate employees and make them more productive (Luthans, 2018; (Xanthopoulou, 2017; Malhotra, 2017; Calvin, 2017).

Employee Performance

Employees who are the most efficient are motivated to perform due to the relationship between rewards and employee performance (Medina, 2002). Rewards may be cash, recognition, or bonuses, and Suesi (2002) states that reward is the key motive to increase employee performance. Osterloh and Frey (2012) states that employees are motivated to monthly rewards to satisfy the social exchange process, Kanfell (1990), Entiwistal (1987) states that 96% of employees feel motivated by organisational rewards, and Freedman (1978) as cited in Rizwan and Ali (2010) states that recognition in a favourable works environment motivates the employee. The employee is an important part of any organisation increasing the performance and can be motivated through financial and non-financial benefits (Holt, 1993).

Compensation should be designed to attract and motivate highly skilled and qualified employees to achieve goals, reducing employee dissatisfaction and increasing turnover, absenteeism, and poor health (Decenzo & Robbins, 1999; Welthel & Davis, 1996 and Davis,1996).

Mabaso and Dlamini (2017) and Ibrahim and Borerhaneoddin (2010) suggest that a good compensation package encourages effective employees to remain in employment for a longer period of time, leading to job satisfaction, commitment and loyalty. Mabaso and Dlamini (2017), Khan et al (2014) and Greenberg and Baron (2008) agree that employee commitment can be enhanced and satisfaction can be improved through adjustments in the compensation package.

Salary and Employee Performance

Salary is a fixed amount of money paid to a worker, usually expressed in annual terms, with no additions for productivity. It is the most important reward an employee receives at work and is essential for effective performance (Idrees et al., 2015; Wilfred, Elijah & Muturi, 2014 and Muogbo, 2013).

Employees view salary as the value of their employer place on them, and the level of appreciation a worker feels can have a direct impact on their motivation (Woods, 2017). Traditional pay systems are based on the job, equality in standard pay, and competitive salaries, but employees are not encouraged to acquire new skills and

are not rewarded if they do. This can lead to redundancy and monotony of work, reducing an organisation's volume of output.

Salary is an important part of total pay for non-executive employees, as it acts as a benchmark for other cash incentives and helps to attract and retain employees. Employers pay above market rates to retain employees, and employees are paid based on their skills and competencies, not job value (Shield, 2017; Swanepoel, 2013; Lynch, 2010 and Shield, 2007). Employers should pay employees market-related salaries to avoid strike and poor performance, regardless of salary inefficiencies (Livingstone, 2009 and Armstrong, 2003).

Incentives and Employee Performance

The use of re-engineering process and worker incentives can have a positive impact on the organisation, allowing employees to become more involved in decision making and multiple jobs to be done simultaneously, allowing for economies of scale and customisation (David et al, 2005 and Judith, 2018). Work is shifted across organisational and international boundaries, controls and checks are instituted, and non-value adding added work is minimized. Reconciliation is minimized by cutting back on external contact points and creating business allowances.

Incentives can be used by organizations to motivate employees to increase productivity or increase their efforts, and can come in the form of monetary and non-monetary payments. Scholars agree that employees are loyal to an organization if their needs and demands are addressed. (Heathfield, 2013 and Judith, 2018).

Financial incentives increase employee loyalty and help organizations maintain good relationships with their employees by offering financial and non-financial compensation, such as profit sharing, bonus, and promotion, and stock ownership. Studies have found that incentives are key in improving employee performance. (Karim & Reddy, 2013; Saleem, 2011 and Milkovich & Newman, 2008).

The importance of employee incentives in firms is not asset portfolios, but employees working as a team to discover, sell and offer service. However, Mlay et al. (2013) failed to show how to reengineer the labour in conjunction with the reengineering process, and Sethi and King (2003) failed to provide any documentation or empirical evidence concerning the effect of reengineering. Capital holding performed a cultural audit, which showed that unwritten rules of conduct appreciated information hoarding and barely acknowledged the customer. To curb these tendencies, high-ranking executive provided a constant flow of information and raised the performance appraisal system to emphasize the new values of teamwork and cooperation. Reengineering was found to increase efficiency and improve customer service, while the most significant outcome of reengineering were better technology and better customer services.

Sethi and King (2003) found a positive relationship between re-engineering process orientation and non-financial performance measures, suggesting that incentives have a significant impact on employee performance. Re-engineering process is a socio-technical approach that helps shape behavior and mind-set through self-management.

Compensation Benefits and Employee Performance

Compensation benefits are payments to employees that enhance their financial position, categorized into base pay and contingent pay. Compensation benefits are indirect financial and non-financial payments employees receive for continuing their employment with the company. Bernardin (2013) defines compensation benefits as indirect forms of compensation that are intended to maintain or improve the quality of life for employees. Gomez et al. (2012) also says that compensation benefits are sometimes called indirect compensation as they are given to employees in form of plan rather than cash to improve their performance. Cascio (2015) classifies benefits into four basic types: supplemental pay benefits, insurance benefits, retirement benefits and personal service and family-friendly benefits. These benefits enhance employee performance in an organisation.

Compensation benefits are linked to extrinsic motivation (external factors) and direct compensation (financial payment). Studies have found that financial compensation does not have an effect on employee performance, but there is a positive relationship between salary and performance. When an employee is motivated, their

performance will improve (Setyadi & Subekti, 2016; Ryan & Deci, 2012; Niode, 2011; Umar, 2011; Khan, Farooq & Ullar, 2010; Mondy, 2008).

Employee Share Ownership Plan and Employee Performance

Studies have found that adoption of an employee share ownership plan has a positive impact on firm performance, boosting employee morale and leading to attractive firm outcomes (Daniel, 2011). ESOPs can harm shareholders due to weak or ineffective management and lack of motivation to increase productivity. Blues and Krus (2003) argue that ESOPs can provide maximum long-term work, and Pugh et al. (2000) provide an example of acquisitions purchased by companies by ESOP. ESOPs can harm shareholders due to weak or ineffective management and lack of motivation to increase productivity. Blues and Krus (2003) argue that ESOPs can provide maximum long-term work, and Pugh et al. (2000) provide an example of acquisitions purchased by companies by ESOP.

Conceptual Framework

Based on the study objectives, the following conceptual relationships are established by the researcher:

Source: Researcher's Model (2023)

The above framework indicates that remuneration is an independent variable, employee performance is the dependent variable, while salary, incentive, compensation benefit and employee stock ownership plan are the dimensions of the independent variable (Remuneration) while Employee Performance is the dependent variables as depicted on frame.

Theoretical Review

The study viewed four theories, they are: Agency Theory, Stakeholders Theory, Social Exchange and Incentive Contract theory.

Agency Theory

Agency theory suggests that firm owners bear expenses by hiring people who manage the organization's affairs, leading to a focus on increasing sales instead of profits and earnings management. This shifts affluence away from the people who own the company and erodes shareholder wealth value (Stephen & Barry, 1973).

ESOPs increase employee ownership, but if new owners have no powers for decision making, existing managers will have more control. Fair remuneration adoption encourages more management monopoly, leading to less corporate performance. ESOPs increase voting power, making hostile takeover beneficial to shareholders.

Stakeholders Theory

Stakeholder's theory is general and comprehensive, guiding the structure and operations of established corporations. The management is obligated to take care of the welfare and interests of diverse parties, and ESOPs adoption is in line with the stakeholder's theory (Evan & Freeman, 1993; Okwuise, 2023).

Social Exchange Theory

(Social-exchange theory suggests that companies that give generous reimbursements stand a higher chance to acquire and maintain employees for their skills to be harnessed. Benefits are a useful means to motivate, retain and attract qualified employees, and can improve firm productivity by making employees more affiliated and attached to the firm (Kurlander & Barton, 2003 and Horwitz et al., 2003).

Incentive Contract Theory

Employees are encouraged to put forth ideas to increase productivity and contribute to the production process, as they are key cogs in the conveyor belt of the production process (Jean & David, 2002). The principle of owning property rights is essential to make and develop assets, as it provides absolute right to make decisions and right to revenues after all encumbrances are settled (Milgrom & Roberts, 1992).

Empirical Review

Aliku, Morka and Igemohia (2020) examined the effect of compensation management on Employees Performance in the Manufacturing Industry in Egypt. A descriptive survey research design was adopted and a sample size of 73 respondents was determined. Data presented and analyzed was dichotomized into three parts: descriptive analysis of respondents profile using simple weighted percentage, descriptive statistics of data gotten from the questionnaire using minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviations, and Pearson correlation analysis. The findings revealed that all the independent variables Salary (SLY) and Benefits Programmes (BP) have a significant relationship with Employees Performance.

Twumasi, Sarpong and Opare (2020) examined the effect of compensation on employee's performance in Accra Technical University: Ghana. Results showed that administrators were not attracted by monetary aspects, but rather management sensitivity to their needs.

Suleiman (2019) examined the relationship between remuneration and service delivery in the hospitality industry in Uganda, a case study of International Hotel Muyenga (IHM). The study was guided by three objectives: to examine the types of staff remuneration in IHM and the level of service quality in IHM, to test Pearson's Correlation Co-efficient Technique, and to consider remuneration, staff development and lecturers service delivery. The findings revealed a positive significant relationship, but an insignificant relationship between planning of general welfare and service delivery of IHM staff. Recommendations were drawn to plan well for remuneration through making fair budgets, put proper training, seminars, conferences into plans, and ignore general welfare as it does not relate with service delivery.

Fitsum (2018) examined the factors affecting the performance of employees in the hotel industry in Eritrea and found a positive and significant relationship between motivation, leadership, employee-employer relationship,

training, and working conditions, with training more prevalent in privately-owned hotels than government hotels.

Judith (2018) examined the effect of incentives on employee performance at Kenya Forest Service, Uasin Gishu County, and using descriptive survey research design. A pilot study was done in Nandi County to test for reliability, and a cronbach alpha of 0.72 was obtained. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze data, which indicated that incentives are essential in organizational performance.

Sunday, Nwekpa and Udu (2018) examined the extent to which salary increase as independent variable (x) influences employee productivity in cement manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. The study adopted survey design and questionnaire were distributed. They found that salary increase has a significant relationship with employee productivity in cement manufacturing firms in South-South, Nigeria. They recommended that salary should be determined and increased based on productivity to create competition and motivate employees.

Fayyaz, Fiza and Ahsan (2017) examined the impact of employee stock ownership plans (ESOPs) on the overall performance of organizations in Karachi, Southern Pakistan. Results showed a statistically significant correlation between ESOPs and overall performance, with employees' turnover having moderate positive significant correlation.

Kimani, Thomas and Arasa (2017) conducted a case study of Mombasa Cement Limited, Kenya to determine the effect of compensation strategies on employee performance. The study used survey research method and a stratified sampling technique to select respondents. Quantitative data was analyzed, presented and interpreted using descriptive statistics. Pearson correlation method was used to evaluate the linear relationship between two continuous variables. The study found that reasonable salary, benefits in form of bonuses and allowances, and recognition through certification or verbally promoted employee performance. It also concluded that employees in the company consider recognition as a means of appreciation and believes that provision of certification awards generally motivates them to perform better.

Murray (2017) examined the effect of remuneration on motivation and performance of employees at the Nation Media Group in Nairobi Kenya. Qualitative research was used to identify variables and a sample size of 100 employees was used. Forty one of the targeted 100 staff responded by returning the questionnaire, indicating that employees are the most important of all the factors of production and if their motivation is low then there will be an influence on their effectiveness and efficiency.

Ojeleye (2017) examined the impact of remuneration on employees' performance, eighty three employees of Abdul Gusau polytechnic and state college of education both in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The study found a strong and positive relationship between remuneration and employees' performance, suggesting prompt payment of salaries, wages and all entitlements and encouragement of participation in pay determination.

Augustina (2016) investigated the effect of ownership of shares by employees on financial performance of listed firms in the NSE, Kenya. The study used purposeful sampling to pick 8 companies with employee stock ownership, and secondary data was exposed to sensitivity analysis using OLS regression. The results showed that ESOPs had a strong positive and significant influence on the financial performance of the companies. Companies should put in place and implement corporate policies to encourage employees to take up ESOPs, and public policy should encourage investors and entrepreneurs to promote broad based ESOPs.

Babagana and Dungus (2015) examined the effects of staff remuneration on the performance of Ramat Polytechnic Maiduguri students from 1995-2011 in Borno State, Nigeria. Thier study found a strong positive relationship between staff remuneration and performance of Ramat Polytechnic Maiduguri students from 1995-2011.

Edirisooriya (2014) examined the impact of extrinsic rewards and intrinsic rewards on employee performance: With Special Reference to ElectriCo Sri Lanka. Self-designed questionnaire was used as the primary data collection method. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics. The representative sample of 100 employees is selected from a population of 1075 employees in the ElectriCo. The

results revealed that there is a positive relationship between extrinsic reward, intrinsic reward and employee performance.

Hameed, Ramzan, Zubair, Ali and Arslan (2014) examined the impact of compensation on employee performance in the banking sector of Pakistan. Their results suggest that compensation has a positive impact on employee performance.

Sajuyigbe, Olaoye and Adeyemi (2013) investigated the impact of reward on employees' performance in selected manufacturing companies in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. Structured questionnaire was used to collect data from one hundred (100) participants through purposive sampling method and data were analyzed by multiple regression analysis with the aid of statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 16. Result showed that reward dimensions jointly predict employees' performance which accounted for 71% variance of performance.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

This section describes the research design, population and sample size, data collection method, research procedures and data analysis methods.

Research Design

The study adopts a descriptive research design. The design is suitable for this study because it is economical, simple, and clear. It also helps in understanding the entire population from the selected part of it. Reliability and validity of data collection methods are tested, as required by descriptive studies.

Practical relations between variables, hypothesis testing, and the development of generalizations across populations are determined using a descriptive research design. The results of descriptive surveys are helpful in that they give information that facilitates practitioners and researchers in explaining how distinctive variables could link to other variables.

Population of the Study

The population of the study are the employees of the selected hotels in Delta State, which are; Elomax Hotel (Asaba), Grand Hotel (Asaba), Top Rank Hotel (Asaba), Vienna International Hotel (Asaba), Brook View Hotels (Warri), Luxury Hotel (Sapele), Gordons Resort Hotel (Sapele), Eliko Hotel (Warri), which amounts to a total of two hundred and twenty six (226) employees. See table 1 for evaluation.

Table 1: Population Distribution

Firm	Location	N0	Staff Strength	Percentage
Elomax Hotel	Asaba	1	63	15.4%
Grand Hotel	Asaba	1	74	18.1%
Top Rank Hotel	Asaba	1	41	10%
Vienna International Hotel	Asaba	1	43	10.5%
Brook View Hotels	Warri	1	49	12%
Eliko Hotel	Warri	1	45	11%
Luxury Hotel	Sapele	1	44	10.8%
Gordons Resort Hotel	Sapele	1	48	11.7%
	Total	8	407	100

Source: Human Resource Department of Selected Hotels (2023)

Sample Size

For the purpose of this study, given a target population of four hundred and seven (407) members, the sample size was derived using the sample size determination formula by Taro Yamene (1973). Taro Yamane developed this formula to calculate or determine the sample size in relation to the population under study. So that

inferences and conclusions reached after the survey can be generalized to the entire population from which the sample was gotten.

Where:

n = sample size

e = level of significance

N = population size

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

The working reveals the desired sample size thus:

$$n = \frac{407}{1 + 407(0.5)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{407}{1 + 407(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{407}{2.0175} = 202$$

The sample size for the study was approximately 202 respondents. A sample size of 202 employees of the target population was used in this research. Just like any other descriptive studies that have been conducted before, this research may experience errors. These are non-observation and observation errors. The errors that may occur from the respondents are non-response errors and response bias. There may also be administrative errors and data processing errors in the process of analyzing data. To allocate the sample size of 202 to the selected hotels in Delta State, the study adopted the Bowley's (1926) proportional allocation formula.

The formula is as stated below:

$$n_h = \frac{nN_h}{N}$$

Where:

n_h = Number of units allocated to each institutions

N_h = Number of employees in each firm stratum in the population

n = Total Sample

N = The total population size under study

Table 2: Sample Size According to Selected Hotels in Delta State

Name of Hotel	Computation	Sample Size Derived
Elomax Hotel	$n_h = \frac{202 \times 63}{407} = 31$	31
Grand Hotel	$n_h = \frac{202 \times 74}{407} = 37$	37
Top Rank Hotel	$n_h = \frac{202 \times 41}{407} = 20$	20
Vienna International Hotel	$n_h = \frac{202 \times 43}{407} = 21$	21
Brook View Hotels	$n_h = \frac{202 \times 49}{407} = 24$	24
Eliko Hotels	$n_h = \frac{202 \times 45}{407} = 23$	23
Luxury Hotel	$n_h = \frac{202 \times 44}{407} = 22$	22
Gordons Resort Hotel	$n_h = \frac{202 \times 48}{407} = 24$	24
TOTAL		202

Source: Survey Analysis (2023)

Sampling Technique

The target respondents were selected using a simple random sampling technique. The individuals from the chosen population shared similar characteristics, like similar operations and similar reward and remuneration schemes. It is identified that there are several advantages to sampling as opposed to a census. These are lower costs, greater accuracy in results, a greater speed of data collection, and a higher availability of population elements. Based on the above assertions, this study adopted a simple random sampling technique. The simple random sampling design was aimed at ensuring high accuracy and precision.

Research Instrument

Structured sets of questionnaire were used as the primary instrument in this study. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A covered the bio data of respondents. Section B covered the dimensions and relevant questions of remuneration and employee performance. The participant were given a period of one week to respond to the various questions without external influence. However the researcher retrieved the copies of questionnaire at the end of one week interval by hand. The response format in five (5) point likert scale, whereby the respondents were asked to give answers ranging from (1) = strongly disagree, (2) = disagree, (3) = undecided, (4) = agree, and (5) = strongly agree, all to measure the chosen variables in the study.

Validity of the Research instrument

It is a measure of how well a test measures what it was supposed to measure. In order to test for the validity of the data collection instruments, the researcher conducted a pilot study, the aim for the pilot study was to get information from professionals from the field of management sciences that enabled the researcher to modify and improve the research instrument.

Reliability of Research Instrument

In order to ensure that the results are reliable, the same sets of questions were asked. Therefore, since all sampled respondents were randomly administered, subject bias was controlled to a large extent. Cronbach's alpha was used to measure reliability to test if the questionnaire is considered reliable and consistent. A reliability coefficient of .7 is acceptable, while the reliability coefficient of .6 and below shows poor reliability (Sekaran, 2003).

Table3: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standard Items	Numbers of items
0.868	0.866	5

Source: Statistical Package for Social Sciences

From the above Table 3, a reliability coefficient of 0.868 and above is higher and is acceptable, while the reliability coefficient of 0.6 and below shows poor reliability (Sekaran, 2011).

Data Collection Method

The study collected data using a self-administered questionnaire. In this proposal, the questionnaire had two distinct parts, Section A and Section B: Section A was used to collect background information about the employees. Section B consists of the main questions that were used to determine the effects of remuneration on employee performance in the hospitality industry. The copies of the questionnaire were left with the respondents for a period of one week before collection. The questionnaire had closed-ended questions measured on a 5-point Likert scale where 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree. Each question allowed the respondents to check "not applicable" if necessary. There were open-ended questions that sought further explanations from the respondents.

Source of Data Collection

Primary data was collected using the structured questionnaire. A questionnaire is used because it manages to collect information from a large number of people in a short period of time and in a relatively cost-effective way. This tool gave room and freedom of expression to the respondents, who expected to get more information to capture important themes of the study on the effects of remuneration on employee performance. The

questionnaire is used to collect data from the employees of the selected organisation under investigation to determine the effects of remuneration on employee performance. The questionnaire was developed based on the research objectives.

Data Analysis Technique

The study edited and coded the collected data. The editing is done in order to detect errors and omissions, ensure data accuracy, be uniformly entered and complete, be consistent with the intent of the question and other information in the survey, and be arranged to simplify coding and tabulation. Alpha-numeric data coding is carried out to assign numbers and other symbols to the questions. It is done in order to group the respondents into a limited number of classes or categories that facilitate efficient analysis. Coded data is tabulated in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) in a frequency distribution table to capture the effect of remuneration on employee performance.

Model Specification

In order to establish the effects of remuneration on employee performance at selected hotels in Delta State, a multiple regression analysis is carried out using the following regression model:

$$Y = f(X_1, X_2, X_3, X_4) \dots \dots \dots \text{Model 1}$$

The mathematical multiple regression equation is as follows:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 1}$$

Where:

Y = Employee Performance.

X1= Salary.

X2= Incentive.

X3= Compensation Benefit.

X4= Employee Stock Ownership Plan.

ϵ = Error term

B₀ = Constant

Apriori expectation: Mathematically it is expected that B₁ to B₄ ≥ 0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Salary has no positive and significant effects on employee performance of selected hotels in Delta State

Tables 4:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.332 ^a	.110	.106	1.6560

a. Predictors: (Constant), Salary (S)

Tables 5:

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	66.393	1	66.393	24.210	.000 ^b
	Residual	534.774	195	2.742		
	Total	601.168	196			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (EP)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Salary (S)

Tables 6:

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	10.890	1.026		10.615	.000
	Salary (S)	.292	.059	.332	4.920	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (EP)

Source: Field Analysis, 2023

From the regression result in the table above, the p-value is less than 0.05. This shows a positive beta value of 0.332 (approximately 33%), which shows that salary (S) has positive and significant effects on employee performance (EP), as the probability value of 0.000 is also less than the critical level of significance (i.e., $P < 0.05$). With these statistics, we reject the null hypothesis and wish to state here that there is a positive and significant effect between salary (S) and employee performance (EP).

Hypothesis Two:

H₀₂: Incentive has no positive and significant effects on employee performance of selected hotels in Delta State.

Tables 7:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.156 ^a	.024	.019	1.7343

a. Predictors: (Constant), Incentive (I)

Tables 8:

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.644	1	14.644	4.868	.029 ^b
	Residual	586.524	195	3.008		
	Total	601.168	196			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (EP)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Incentive (I)

Tables 9:

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.575	1.063		12.775	.000
	Incentive (I)	.143	.065	.156	2.206	.029

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (EP)

Source: Field Analysis, 2023

In the tables above, even when the p-value is greater than 0.05, this shows a positive beta value of 0.156 (approximately 16%), which shows that incentive (I) has a significant effect on employee performance (EP) (i.e., $P > 0.05$). These statistics indicate that we reject the null hypothesis and state here that incentives (I) significantly affect employee performance (EP).

Hypothesis Three:

H₀₃: Compensation benefits have no positive and significant effects on employee performance of selected hotels in Delta State.

Tables 10:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.188 ^a	.035	.030	1.7245

a. Predictors: (Constant), Compensation (C)

Table 11:

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	21.271	1	21.271	7.153	.008 ^b
	Residual	579.897	195	2.974		
	Total	601.168	196			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (EP)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Compensation (C)

Table 12:

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	13.269	.993		13.364	.000
	Compensation (C)	.159	.059	.188	2.674	.008

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (EP)

Source: Field Analysis, 2023

In the tables above, even when the p-value is greater than 0.05 ($P = 0.008$), it still shows a positive beta value of 0.188 (approximately 19%), which shows that compensation (C) has a significant effect on employee performance (EP) (i.e., $P > 0.05$). With these statistics, we reject the null hypothesis and state here that compensation (C) significantly has effects on employee performance (EP).

Hypothesis Four:

H₀₄: Employee stock ownership plan has no positive and significant effects on employee performance of selected hotels in Delta State.

Tables 13:

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.129 ^a	.017	.012	1.7411

a. Predictors: (Constant), Employee stock ownership plan (ESOP)

Table 14:

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	10.045	1	10.045	3.314	.070 ^b
	Residual	591.123	195	3.031		
	Total	601.168	196			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (EP)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Employee stock ownership plan (ESOP)

Table 15:

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
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		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	14.389	.841		17.108	.000
	Employee stock ownership plan (ESOP)	.088	.048	.129	1.820	.070

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (EP)

Source: Field Analysis, 2023

The results presented in the tables above show that even when the p-value is greater than 0.05 (P = 0.07), it exhibits a positive beta value of 0.129 (approximately 13%), which shows that the employee stock ownership plan (ESOP) has a significant effect on employee performance (EP) (i.e., P > 0.05). With these statistics, we reject the null hypothesis and state here that employee stock ownership plans (ESOP) significantly affect employee performance. This revealed that 13% (0.129) of the variance in employee performance (EP) is explained by the employee stock ownership plan (ESOP), with an adjusted r² value of 0.012.

Table 16: Results of dimensions of remuneration and its significant effects on Employee Performance

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.345 ^a	.119	.101	1.6607

a. Predictors: (Constant), Salary (S), Incentive (I) Compensation (C), Employee Stock Ownership Plan (ESOP)

Table 17:

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	71.657	4	17.914	6.496	.000 ^b
	Residual	529.510	192	2.758		
	Total	601.168	196			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance (EP)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Salary (S), Incentive (I) Compensation (C), Employee Stock Ownership Plan (ESOP)

Table 18:

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.837	1.390		7.075	.000
	Salary	-.034	.053	-.050	-.631	.529
	Incentive	.061	.063	.073	.974	.331
	Compensation	.064	.068	.070	.950	.343
	Employee Stock Ownership Plan	.267	.070	.304	3.790	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Field Analysis, 2023

The results in Table 18 above show that the tested variables exhibited positive coefficients ranging from 0.073 to 0.304, implying that there is a significant effect association between the studied variables of remuneration and employee performance. Also, apart from knowledge management, which had a negative beta value of -0.050, salary, incentive, compensation, and the employee stock ownership plan all exhibited positive beta values. Amongst all, salary seems to be the most significant variable to employee performance.

Discussion of Results

The results of the regression analysis showed that incentives, as a measure of remuneration, have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, as evidenced by the beta value of the standardised coefficients.

This corroborates the findings of Muogbo (2013), who found that attractive salaries are valuable tools for increasing employee performance and the productivity of an organisation. To motivate people to put in maximum efforts, it is essential that their needs are met as far as is practicable.

Incentives have a positive effect on employee performance in the Nigerian hospitality industry, with a positive beta value of 16% and a p-value greater than the critical value of 0.005. This is in agreement with the findings of Saleem (2011), who asserts that financial incentives increase employee loyalty in the organization. Organisations should seek to maintain good relationships with their employees by offering incentives in the form of financial and non-financial compensation, such as profit sharing, bonuses, and promotion. Compensation benefits have a positive and significant effect on employee performance, even when the p-value is greater than 0.005. This agrees with the findings of Khan, Farooq, and Ullar (2010) that there is a direct and positive relationship between financial compensation and employee performance.

The results of the fourth objective showed that an employee stock ownership plan is significantly linked to employee performance, with 13% of variance explained by knowledge management. This aligns with the study of Daniel (2011), which found that an employee stock ownership plan boosts employee morale and leads to good employee behavior and perceptions, leading to attractive firm outcomes in the form of profitability and customer contentment. From the foregoing, it has been statistically and empirically established that all measures, proxies, and indicators of remuneration used in this study have a statistically significant positive effect on employee performance, as evidenced in existing literature.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The study found that remuneration has a significant and positive effect on employee performance in the Nigerian hospitality industry, and that organizations should focus on their remuneration plans to motivate employees to have positive attitudes and contribute positively towards organizational goals.

Recommendations

From the outcome of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The study recommends that firms review the wage structure in order to motivate employees to retain their jobs and increase performance.
- ii. Organisations should seek to maintain good relationships with their employees by offering good incentives in the form of financial and non-financial compensation.
- iii. For organisations that do not have remuneration systems in place, a lot of informative awareness and campaigning should be done to enable the workforce to see reasons and appreciate why compensation is necessary both for employees as well as other stakeholders as a cooperative entity.
- iv. Provide stock incentives and increase motivational measures and the commitment of employees due to employee ownership in the organisation, which is expected to increase employee productivity and overall organisation performance.

REFERENCES

- Abosede, A. J. & Adekunle, O. A. (2012). Reward system as a predictor of workers job performance: A case of health workers in Lagos State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Behaviour Sciences*, 2(1), 7-17.
- Adeniyi, A.O. (2013). Salary and wages and employee motivation in Nigeria service industry. *Scottish Journal of Arts, Social Sciences and Scientific Studies*, 2(2), 89-98.
- Agburu, J.I. (2012). Recent Trends in Wage and Salary Administration in Nigeria: A Synopsis on Theoretical and Empirical Challenges. *International Journal of Basic and Applied Science*; 1(2), 257-268
- Alaba, R. A. & Owodunni, A. (2017). Personnel testing and selection in organization. Lagos: Triumph publishers.

- Ali, M., & Raza, S.A. (2015). Factors affecting to select Islamic Credit Cards in Pakistan: The TRA Model. MPRA Paper, No. 64037, University Library of Munich, German.
- Aliku, I, Morka T, & Igemohia, F. (2020). Compensation Management and Employee Performance: Manufacturing Industry in Focus. *Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology* 17(7), 8792-8810. ISSN 1567-214x.
- Allen, D. G., Bryant, P. C., & Vardaman, J. M. (2010). Retaining talent: Replacing misconceptions with evidence-based strategies. *Academy of management Perspectives*, 24(2), 48-64.
- Armstrong, M. (2003). *A handbook of human resource management practice*; (9th ed.). London: Cambrian Printer Ltd.
- Armstrong, M. (2005). *A Handbook on Human Resources Management Practices*; UK; Kogan page, 986
- Armstrong, M. (2008). *Strategic Human Resource Management: A Guide to Action*. Philadelphia: Kogan Page Publishers.
- Armstrong, M. (2016). *A handbook of Human Resource Management Practice*. 11th ed. Philadelphia: Kogan Page Limited
- Avey, J. B., Wernsing, T. S., & Luthans, F. (2018). Can positive employees help positive organizational change? Impact of psychological capital and emotions on relevant attitudes and behaviors. *The journal of applied behavioral science*, 44(1), 48-70.
- Azasu, S (2017). Rewards and performance of Swedish real estate firms, *Compensation & Benefits Review*, 41(4): 19-28
- Babagana, A. & Dungus, B. (2015). Staff Remuneration and the Performance of Ramat Polytechnic Maiduguri Students from 1995 to 2011 *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Management Sciences*. 3(5)1-10
- Bakker, A. B. & Demerouti, E. (2016). The job demands–resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22. 309-328.
- Bakker, A. B., Hakanen, J. J., Demerouti, E. & Xanthopoulou, D. (2017). Job resources boost work engagement, particularly when job demands are high”. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 99. 274–284.
- Bartkus, R.B. (1997). Employee Ownership as catalyst of Organizational Change. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*. 10(4). 331 – 344
- Bauer, T. N., Erdogan, B., Liden, R. C. & Wayen, S. J. (2016). A Longitudinal Study of the Moderating Role of Extraversion: Leader-Member Exchange, Performance, and Turnover During New Executive Development. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 91, 298-310.
- Bhattacharya, M.S. & Nilanjan S. (2009). *Compensation Management*. New Delhi: Excel Books.
- Becker et al., (1996). *Employee Stock Ownership Plans: Employee Compensation and Firm Value*.
- Bohan, F. (2004). Hidden power of productivity: Improving productivity by 30.
- Brown, D. (2003). Reward Strategies. *Journal of Personnel Management*, 1, 17-29.
- Brown, M. P., Sturman, M. C., & Simmering, M. J. (2003). Compensation policy and organizational performance: The efficiency, operational, and financial implications of pay levels and pay structure. *Academy of Management Journal*, 46(6), 752-762.
- Christensen, A. L. (2011). Linking Ethical Leadership to Employee Performance: The Role of Leader Member Exchange, Self-Efficacy, and Organizational Identification”. *Organizational Behaviour and Human Decision Process*, 115(2). 204-213.
- Calvin, O. Y. (2017). The Impact of Remuneration on Employees' Performance (A Study of Abdul Gusau Polytechnic, Talata-Mafara and State College of Education Maru, Zamfara State). *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review*. Nigerian Chapter, 4(2), 34-43.
- Cantoni, C.J. (1997). Learn to manage pay and performance like an entrepreneur. *Compensation and Benefits Review*, 29(1), 52-8.
- Cascio, W. F. (2015). *Managing Human Resources: Productivity; Quality of Work Life, Profits*. McGraw-Hill/Irwin, Avenue of the Americas, New York, NY, 10020.

- Clarkson, M.B. (1991). Defining, evaluating and managing corporate social performance: A stakeholder model. In J.E Post (Ed.), *Research in corporate social performance and policy*: 331- 358.
- Chen, W.J. (2013). Factors Influencing Internal Service Quality at International Tourist Hotels, *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 35, 152-160.
- Chow, I. H. S., & Liu, S. S. (2009). The effect of aligning organizational culture and business strategy with HR systems on firm performance in Chinese enterprises. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20(11), 2292-2310.
- Cole, G. (2012). *Personnel and Human Resources Management*, Thomas Learning, high Holborn House, 50-51 Bedford Row, London WC1R4LR
- Cooper, R. & Schindler P. (2001). *Business Research methods*, Boston, McGraw- Hill Irwin 7th Edition, 132 - 225.
- Coyle, S. J. A. & Conway, N. (2014). The Employment Relationship through the Lens of Social Exchange”. In Shapiro, J. A. M., Shore, L. M. Taylor, S. M. & Tetrick, L. (Eds.). *The Employment Relationship: Examining Psychological and Contextual Perspectives*. Oxford, UK. Oxford University Press. 5-28
- Crossman, A. & Zaki, A. (2003). Job Satisfaction and Employee Performance of Lebanese Banking Staff”. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 18(4). 368-376.
- Danish, R.Q & Usman, A. (2010). Impact of Reward and Recognition on Job Satisfaction and Motivation. An empirical study from Pakistan. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5, 159-167.
- Decenzo, D.A. & Robbins, P.S. (1999). *Human Resource Management* (6thed.). New York: John Wiley and Sons, Inc.
- Decenzo, D.A., Jones, G., & Robbins, S.P. (2016). In: 3rd, ed. *Personnel Human Resource Management. India: Prentice-Hall Ltd*, 424-470.
- De Nissi, A. S. & Griffin, R. W. (2014). *Human Resource Management*. New York: Houghton Mifflin.
- Denis, C., & Michel, M. (2011). Fits in strategic human resource management and methodological challenge: Empirical evidence of the influence of empowerment and compensation practices on human resource performance in Canadian firms. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20(4), 738-770.
- Dessler, G. (2016). *Human Resource Management*. 12th ed. New Jersey: Price Hall.
- Dessler, G. (2011). *Human Resource Management, (12th ed.)*. New Jersey: Prince Hall. East African Centre for Law and Justice, ‘Devolution (Implementation and Challenges) (as of 26 October 2011) 7 February 2014.
- Detert, J. R., Trevino, L. K., Burris, E. R. & Andiappan, M. (2017). Managerial modes of influence and counter productivity in organizations: A longitudinal business unit-level investigation”. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92. 993–1005.
- Dhiman, R.K. & Gupta, S.K. (2008). Post - financial performance: a study of Indian ESOP pharmaceutical corporate sector. *International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research*, 1(1), 180-191. 43
- Edirisooriya, W. A. (2014). Impact of Rewards on Employee Performance: With Special Reference to ElectriCo. Reshaping Management and Economic Thinking through Integrating Eco-Friendly and Ethical Practices. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Management and Economics*. Faculty of Management and Finance, University of Ruhuna, Sri Lanka
- Fadugba, F. (2012). Incentive Systems in Software Organizations, ICSEA 2009 - *The Fourth International Conference on Software Engineering Advances*, Porto, Portugal. September 2009.
- Fitsum, G. (2018). Factors Influencing Employee Performance in Hotel-A Comparative Study of Government and Privately Owned Hotels in Eritrea” *International Journal of Research in Business Studies and Management*, 5(11), 2018, 1-9.
- Gerhart, B., & Milkovich, G.T. (1990). Organizational Differences in Managerial Compensation and Financial Performance. *The Academy of Management Journal*. 33, 663-691

- Geralyn M. F. (2017). *Human Resource Management Basic: Small verses Large Firm Practices*. Virginia Hernandez. The University of Texas of Premium Basis.
- George, D. (2016). The incentive effects of monitoring under alternative compensation schemes. *International Journal of Industrial Organization*
- Gichuru, C., (2015). Effects of Motivational Incentives on Employee Performance in Small and Medium Enterprises in Kenya: A Case Study of Family Bank, Unpublished Master's Thesis, Technical University of Kenya, Nairobi
- Greenberg, J. & Baron, R.A. (2018). *Behaviour in Organizations* .9th Edn..Pearson Education Inc, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey.
- Hallock, D.E., Salazar, R.J. & Venneman, S. (2014). Demographic and attitudinal correlates of employee satisfaction with an ESOP. *British Journal of Management*, 15(4): 321-333.
- Hameed, A., Ramzan, M., Zubair, H. M. K., Ali, G. & Arslan, M. (2014). Impact of Compensation on Employee Performance (Empirical Evidence from Banking Sector of Pakistan). *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. 5(2);302-309
- Namasivayam, K., Miao, L., & Zhao, X. (2007). An Investigation of the Relationship between Compensation Practices and Firms Performance in the US Hotel Industry. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 26, 574-587
- Hameed Z, Maqbool A, Athar M. R, Ijaz M.S & Hassan E. (2013). How to Increase Employee Performance: Investigating the Impact of Incentive Motivators and Organization-Based Self-Esteem in a Pakistani Perspective, *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research* 14(5) accessed from [http://www.idosi.org/mejsr/mejsr_14\(5\)13/16.pdf](http://www.idosi.org/mejsr/mejsr_14(5)13/16.pdf) in March 2016.
- Harrison, D.A., & Liska, Z. (2018). Promoting Regular Exercise Occupational Fitness Programme. *Journal of Personnel Psychology*, 5(5), 27-45.
- Heathfield, S. M. (2013). *What Are incentives at work?* Retrieved from, <http://www.humanresources.about.com/od/employeerecognition/g/what-areincentives-at-work.htm>
- Henderson, L. N., & Tulloch, J. (2018). Incentives for retaining and motivating health workers in Pacific and Asian countries. *Human resources for health*, 6(1), 18.
- Heneman, R. L., Tansky, J. W. & Camp, S. M. (2010). Human resource management practices in small and medium-sized enterprises: Unanswered questions and future research perspectives. *Entrepreneurship: Theory & Practice*, 25, 11-25.
- Herzberg, M. B. & Snyderman, B. B. (1999). *The Motivation to Work*, 3rd edition, Transaction, Publishers, New Brunswick.
- Hewitt, A. (2019). Managing Performance with incentive pay. *Journal of Personnel Management*, 7(1), 20-31.
- Homans, G.C. (1958). Social behavior as exchange. *American Journal of Sociology*, 63(6), 597-606.
- Ibrahim, I.I. & Borerhaneoddin, A. (2010). Is job satisfaction mediating the relationship between compensation structure and organizational commitment? A study in the Malaysian power utility. *J.Global Bus.Econ.* , 1:43- 61.
- Idemobi, E.I., Onyeizugbe, C.U., & Akpunonu, E.O. (2011). Compensation management as a tool for improving organizational performance in the Public Sectors: A study of the Civil Service of Anambra State of Nigeria. *Sacha Journal of Policy and Strategic Studies*, 1(1), 109-120.
- Idrees, Z., Xinpeng, X., Shafi, K., Hua, L. & Nazeer, A. (2015). Effect of salary, training and motivation on job performance of employees. *American Journal of Business and Management*, 3(2), 55-58.
- Ines, K., & Canales, P. (2015). Compensation and control sales policies and sales performance: the field sales manager's points of view. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*, 26(4), 273-285.
- Ivancevich, J.M. (2004). Human resource management. (9th ed). New York: McGraw Hill.
- Jensen, M., & Meckling W. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics* 3: 305 – 360
- Judith, C. (2018). Effect of Incentives on Employee Performance at Kenya Forest Service Uasin Gishu County. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM)* 20.3 (2018): 26-32.

- Kanzunnudin, M. (2017). Effect of wages and supervision of employee productivity: A case Study on PT Tonga Tiur Son Zenith District Kragan. *Fokus Ekonomi*, 2(1), 11-20.
- Khan, M.S., I. Khan, G. M. Kundi, S. Khan, A. Nawaz, F. Khan & Yar, N.B. (2014). The impact of job satisfaction and organizational commitment on the intention to leave among the academicians. *Int. J. Acad. Res. Bus.Social Sci.*, 4:114-131.
- Khan, U.K., Farooq, U.S., & Ullar, I.M. (2010). The Relationship between Rewards and Employee Motivation in Commercial Banks of Pakistan. *Research Journal of International Studies*, 6(4): 37-46.
- Kinicki, A. & Kreitner, R. (2017). *Organizational behaviour*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Kinicki, A. & Williams, B. K., (2018). *Management: A practical introduction* (3rd Ed.) New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Knippenberg, D., Dick, R. & Tavares, S. (2017). Social identity and social exchange: Identification, support, and withdrawal from the job”. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*. 37, 457–477, 2007.
- Kurlander, P. & Barton, S. (2003). Benefits performance? *Workspan*, 46(11), 31-6.
- Lazear, E. P. (1986). Salaries and piece rates. *Journal of Business*, 59: 405-31.
- Levine, D.I., & Tyson, L.D. (1990). Participation, productivity and the firm's environment’, in Alan S. Blinder (ed.) *Paying for Productivity: A Look at the Evidence*, The Brookings Institution: Washington, DC.
- Lipold, A.G. (2012). Benefit integration boosts productivity and profits. *Workforce*, 81, 46-50.
- Livingstone, D. (2019). *Education and jobs: Exploring the gaps*. Canada: University of Toronto Press.
- Long, R.J. (2017). *Strategic Compensation in Canada* (3rd ed.), Toronto: Thomson Nelson.
- Luthans, F., Norman, S. M., Avolio, B. J. & Avey, J. B. (2008). The Mediating Role of Psychological Capital in the Supportive Organizational Climate Employee Performance Relationship”. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 29. 219-238.
- Lynch, P. (2010). Time based pay in O. N. Wilfred, C. M. Elijah, & W. M Muturi, (ed). Effect of remuneration on employee performance in the ministry of internal security: A case of Kisii. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*. 4(1), 223-231.
- Mabaso C. M. & Dlamini B. I. (2017). Impact of compensation and benefits on job satisfaction. *Res. J. Business Manage.* 11: 80-90
- Malhotra, N., Budhwar, P. & Prowse, P. (2017). Linking Rewards to Commitment: An Empirical Investigation of Four UK Call Centre’s”. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*. 18(12). 2095-2128.
- Masterson, S. S., Lewis, K., Goldman, B. M. & Taylor, M. S. (2010). Integrating justice and social exchange: The differing effects of fair procedures and treatment on work relationships”. *Academy of Management Journal*. 43. 738–748,
- Mathieu, L & Zajac, O (1990). Employee stock ownership plans, firm performance, and monitoring by outside block holders. *Financial Management*.
- Mayson, S. & Barrett, R. (2016). Getting and keeping good staff: An analysis of human resource management “problems” in small firms. *Report to CPA Australia*, 23(4), 56-78.
- Milgrom, P., & Roberts, J. (1992). *Economics, Organization, and Management*. Prentice-Hall International (UK) Limited: London.
- Mondy, R.W. (2018). *Human Resource Management* (10th ed.). New Jersey: Pearson Prentice Hall
- Muogbo, U. S., (2013). The impact of employee motivation on organizational performance: A study of some selected firms in Anambra State Nigeria. *The International Journal of Engineering and Science*, 2(7), 70-80.
- Mlay, S. V., Zlotnikova, I., & Watundu, S. (2013). *A Quantitative Analysis of Business Process*
- Nel, P.S., Warner, P. Poisat, T. Sono, A.J. Plessis, D & Nqalo, O. (2011). *Human Resource Management*, Oxford University Press, Cape Town.
- Ohene A., Twumasi, A., Sarpong, E., & Opare, D. (2020). The Effect of Compensation on Employees’ Performance: *International Journal of Managerial Studies and Research (IJMSR)*, 8(6), June 2020, PP

- Ojeleye, Y. C. (2017). The impact of remuneration on employees' Performance. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Nigerian Chapter)*, 4(2), 2017
- Okwuse, U. Y., Ugherughe, J. E. & Afunwa, D. (2017). Strategic financial innovations and performance of oil firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 11(1), 73-88.
- Okwuse, U. Y. , Kifordu, A. A. & Oghoghomeh, T. (2020). Impact of conflict management strategies on employee performance in the Nigeria banking industry. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(08), 5167-5177.
- Okwuse, U. Y., Oghoghomeh, T. & Kifordu, A. A. (2020). The impact of talent management strategy on the FMCGS performance in Nigeria. *Test Engineering & Management*, 83(May-Jun), 26981-26992.
- Okwuse, U. Y. (2023). Strategic Planning and performance of health establishments in Delta State: Moderating role of organizational culture. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 5(2), 33-40. DOI:10.51594/ijmer.v5i1.433.
- Okwuse, U. Y. & Ugherughe, J. E. (2023). Organizational climate and employee commitment in the Nigerian tourism sector. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 5(1), 99-114. DOI:10.51594/ijmer.v5i2.434.
- Olubusayo, G. H., Stephen, I. B., & Maxwell, O. (2014). Incentive packages and employees' attitude to work: A study of selected government parastatals in Ogun State, South-West, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 3(1), 63-74.
- Ong, S. & Teh, H. (2012). *Reward System and Performance within Malaysian Manufacturing* Ray, L., (2016). *How does salary affect a worker's productivity?* Retrieved from www.smallbusiness.chron.com/salary-affect-worker-productivity-38126.html.
- Peterson, S. J., Luthans, F., Avolio, B. J., Walumbwa, F. O. & Zhang, Z. (2011). Psychological Capital and Employee Performance: A Latent Growth Modeling Approach. *Personnel Psychology*. 64(2), 287-315
- Pugh, W.N., Oswald, S.L. & Jahera, J.S. (2010). The effect of ESOP adoptions on corporate performance: are there really performance changes? *Managerial and Decision Economics*, 21: 167–180. doi: 10.1002/mde.971
- Rauf, A. M. (2007). HRM sophistication and Small and Medium Performance. *A case of readymade garment manufacturers and exporters in Lohore. Patistan. Thesis .published.*
- Ray, S. & Ray, A.I. (2011). Human resource management practice and its effect on employee's job satisfaction: A study on selected small and medium sized iron and steel firms in India. *Public Policy Admin. Res*, 1:22- 31.
- Robison, D. (1990). Civil Service Pay in Africa, International Labour Office, Geneva.
- Romanoff, K., (2008). What is the difference between a bonus and an Incentive? Retrieved on 25th August, 2016 from http://theperfectpayplan.typepad.com/the_salary_sage/2008/07/what-is-the-dif.html
- Ryan, R. & Madn Deci, E. I. (2012). Self-determination Theory and the facilitation of Intrinsic Motivation, Social Development and Well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55, 68 -78.
- Sajuyigbe, A. S., Olaoye, B .O. & Adeyemi, M.A. (2013). Impact of Reward on Employees Performance in a Selected Manufacturing Companies in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*. 2(2); 27-32
- Saleem S. (2011) the Impact of Financial Incentives on Employees Commitment; *European Journal of Business and Management* 3(4), 258

- Schell, C.M. & Solomon, J.M. (2017). Charismatic leadership and task feedback: A laboratory study of their effects on self-efficacy and task performance. *Leadership Quarterly*, 10(3), 375-396.
- Setyadi, D. & Subekti A. (2016). The Implication of Financial Compensation and Performance Appraisal System to Job Satisfaction and Motivation also Employee Performance in PT Pupuk Kalimantan Timur Indonesia: *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 5(2), 16-27
- Sheridan, P., (2015). *Show me the money: Salary levels have greatest impact on job satisfaction*. Retrieved from www.news.rice.edu/2005/11/10/show-me-the-money-salary-level-have-greatest-impact-on-job-satisfaction/.
- Shields, J., Brown, M., Kaine, S., Samuel, C., Samardzic, A., McLean, P., Johns, R. Leary, P., Plimmer, G. & Robinson, J. (2015). *Managing Employee Performance & Reward: Concepts, Practices, Strategies*. 2nd Edition. Cambridge University Press. London.
- Shield, J. (2017). *Managing employee performance and reward concepts, practices, strategies*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- SHIK, H. (2017). Factors Influencing Employee's Performance in Hotel Industry, *International Journal of Research*, 4(7), 1142-1157.
- Smith, G. (1776). Employee stock ownership and participation in South Korea: Incidence, productivity effects, and prospects. *Review of Development Economics* 6, 263–283.
- Surbhi, S. (2015). Differences between Salaries and Wages. Retrieved on 24th August, 2016 from <http://keydifferences.com/difference-between-salary-andwages.html#ixzz4IG1CT6Vu>
- Swanepoel, B. (2013). *Human resource management: Theory and practice* (3rd ed.). Landsdowne: Juta.
- Swanepoel, B.J, Schenk,T & Tshilongamulenzhe,T. (2014). *South Africa Human Resource Management: Theory and Practice*. (4th, Ed.), Juta, Capetown.
- Taylor, C. (2009). *How does productivity influence wages and salary?* Retrieved from www.smallbusiness.chron.com/productivity-influence-factors-wages-salar-39355.html.
- Tesfaye, O & Debela, p. (2019). Business process reengineering in Ethiopian public organizations: the relationship between theory and practice. *JBAS* 1(2) 21.
- Thomas D. & Lee E. (1995). The Stakeholder Theory of the Corporations, Evidence, and Implications: *The Academy of Management Practice*, 20(1) 65- 91.
- Turner, K. L., & Makhija, M. V. (2006). The role of organizational controls in managing knowledge. *Academy of management review*, 31(1), 197-217.
- Vlachos, I. (2018). The effect of human resource practices on organizational performance: evidence from Greece. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 19(1), 74-97.
- Wayne, S. J., Shore, L. M., Bommer, W. H. & Tetrick, L. E. (2002). The role of fair treatment and rewards in perceptions of organizational support and leader–member exchange". *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 87, 590–598.
- Werner, S. & Ward, S.G. (2014). Recent compensation research: An eclectic review. *Human Resource Management Review*, 14, 201-227.
- Wilfred, O. N., Elijah, C. M. & Muturi, W. M. (2014). Effect of remuneration on employees performance in the ministry of internal security: A case of Kisii. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*. 4(1), 223-231.
- Woods, L. (2016). *How can salary influence a worker's performance in an administration*. Retrieved from www.work.com/can-salary-influence-workers-performance-administration-25950.html.
- Xanthopoulou, D., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E. & Schaufeli, W. B. (2017). The role of personal resources in the job demands resources model". *International Journal of Stress Management*, 14, 121–141.
- Xanthopoulou, D., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E. & Schaufeli, W. B. (2017). Work engagement and financial returns: A diary study on the role of job and personal resources. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*. 82. 183–200.

Zhang, P. (2016). A Study of the Factors That Affect Employee Performance in the UK Hotels, *Thesis Masters of Business Administration*, California State Polytechnic University, Pomona. Zinbarg, M. (2005), *Research Methods*, 2nd ed., Pearson Publishers.